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KNOWLEDGE DYNAMICS IN PROJECT-BASED LEARNING: AN ETHNOGRAPHIC CASE STUDY OF MULTI-DISCIPLINARY ENGINEERING GRADUATE STUDENT TEAMS

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ABSTRACT

What is going on in student project teams? How do students acquire, exchange, and integrate the knowledge necessary to collectively perform a given task? Although knowledge dynamics play a decisive role in project-based learning (PBL), they may happen during and/or between classes and thus take on diverse forms that are often difficult to track for students and teachers. Based on ethnographic research with in-

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situ observations and interviews, this paper sheds light on the knowledge dynamics of engineering graduate students in PBL courses beyond formal design reviews and graded project deliverables. The overall plot of the PBL-course mirrored quasi-real industrial work processes where lecturers acted as potential investors from industry. Our data suggest that knowledge dynamics in this context are related to two factors: (1) the individual student's learning aspirations and (2) the evolving salience of distinct (functional) roles and knowledge resources amongst the team members. We have distilled the findings into an improved educational concept to support working and learning in product development projects and will discuss the potential of ethnographic methods for research in and evaluation of PBL. In reaction to the pandemic, we have furthermore re-designed the concept to support online learning.

1 INTRODUCTION

Given the convergence of mechanics, electrics/electronics, software, and services in product design, product development increasingly demands the combined effort and knowledge exchange of different disciplines. This is not only a challenge for product development teams in industry, but also for university instructors who want to convey the necessary skills to their students. To do so, they, for instance, use project-based learning (PBL). Based on previous studies and conceptual considerations about knowledge dynamics in engineering teams [1] we report results of an ethnographic study to gain deeper insights into the everyday knowledge dynamics of students in PBL courses that is not captured in formal design reviews and graded project deliverables. We have distilled the findings into an improved educational concept to support working and learning in product development projects and will discuss the potential of ethnographic methods for research in and evaluation of PBL.

This paper commences with an overview of related work in the field and the set-up of the PBL course for our case study (Section 2). A description of the ethnographic study design (Section 3) is followed by the presentation of the results (Section 4), which are discussed in section 5 followed by concluding remarks (section 6).

2 BACKGROUND

2.1. Knowledge Dynamics and PBL

As knowledge is generated and applied by individuals in groups, successful product development teams must be able to share and negotiate increasingly heterogenous knowledge [1]. To convey the necessary skillset and to increase students' job readiness [2], PBL, which engages students in meaningful projects and the development of real-world products, has become a central element of engineering education [3; 4]. Consequently, several frameworks have come to the fore [5] and recent publications discuss the issues associated with PBL in engineering education [6] and the current status of PBL in Europe [7]. Other studies have focused on the perspective and experiences of teaching staff in PBL [8; 9] and the student's perspective on PBL in relation to specific topics such as sustainability [10;11], collaboration [12], and motivation [13]. To our knowledge, there is no research to date on what graduate students actually do

in PBL engineering education projects in relation to the knowledge activities they perform. Although field-based methods such as in-situ observations are ideally suited to shed light on actual work practices, they have so far played a marginal role in the evaluation of PBL (a recent review by Guo et al. [14] reported that only two out of 76 studies have used observation-based methods).

2.2. PBL in a multidisciplinary Engineering Project Seminar

The engineering project seminar in focus is specifically designed to train students abilities for knowledge integration and to foster collaboration within multi-disciplinary teams. A project team comprises 9-12 students and works through the entire product development process from the initial idea to the implementation of a real prototype. The members of the project teams have different engineering backgrounds and are enrolled in either of two modules. Both modules are part of the engineering Masters programs at TU Berlin and have either a management focus (“Development and Management of Digital Product Creation Processes (EMP)”) or a development oriented focus (“Applications of Industrial Information Technology (AIIT)”). The combination of these two modules within a single PBL set-up (fig. 1) provides students with an opportunity to experience the challenges arising from the different tasks, interests and priorities that can be found in actual product development projects in the industry.

Figure 1: Overview of project team compositions in the PBL Course

The projects we studied ran from October 2019 until February 2020 (Winter Semester 2019/20). In total 47 students (22 from the EMP module, 25 from the AIIT module) formed 5 project teams. Their main task was to design and develop sustainable products with a socially relevant functionality. The product should support mental activity and learning for young children or help to maintain the memory capabilities of elderly people. The overall outline of the course mirrored quasi-real industrial work processes and functions: the lecturers acted as potential investors from industry during the design reviews and the project teams were given a budget to procure the parts required to produce a prototype. In two design reviews the teams presented their ideas and had to defend their concepts in challenging discussions as if their team would compete for the investment. The product concept and final prototype were assessed on the basis

of ecological sustainability (use of sustainable materials) and economical sustainability (needing as few money as possible), the fit-to-purpose of the product (stimulation of cognitive ability) and the operational performance during the project (team work, division of work time). In order to gain insights into how the project teams worked and the knowledge dynamics within them, an ethnographic study design was applied.

3 METHODOLOGY

3.1. Research Design

Ethnography is a method originating in the social sciences. The idea is to gain insights into practices through presence in the social setting of interest, that is, by “walking a mile in the shoes of others” [15]. For research on students’ activities in PBL-courses we used in-situ observations, as this method allows for maximal flexibility to adapt data collection to the dynamics of project team interactions.

The study design was developed as part of a research seminar for advanced students in the Human Factors (HF) MSc. degree at TU Berlin. A small group of eight HF students was trained to apply ethnographic methods and then assigned as participant observers to one of the five engineering student PBL project teams for the duration of one semester. The research question focused on the knowledge-related activities among the team members. The project teams were fully informed about the purpose of the study and that student researchers participated in the project team meetings, observed construction sessions, and were included in the communication threads before the design reviews. The researching students were often seen as part of the team, which enabled them to experience the everyday work of the PBL-course participants. They also conducted semi-structured interviews with members of the PBL teams based on an interview guide jointly developed with the course instructors to complement the observational data. The data collection took place from October 2019 to February 2020 and encompasses 160 hours of observation and 40 interviews (each lasting 20-30 minutes). The interviews were held with 4-5 members from each team. The HF students chose their interlocutors on the basis of the observed interaction activities and mixed views from active and more quiet team members. Partially the same students were interviewed twice (i.e. at the beginning and the end of the project) to get first-hand views on the transition of roles and responsibilities within the group.

3.2. Data Analysis

Data analysis was inspired by Grounded Theory [16] with several data coding iterations, using a software for qualitative data analysis (AtlasTI Version). Each student initially reviewed their own ethnographic data and then developed a first set of emic codes, i.e., data-driven code categories. In joint data analysis workshops we deduced recurring topics and patterns related to Knowledge Dynamics from the initial codes. Then, a more analytical perspective was developed to come up with conceptually-driven codes. These codes were grouped and re-grouped over the course of the analysis process, and the results from the individual HF-student projects were then collated into two overarching themes consisting of multiple subthemes.

4 RESULTS

In the following, we elaborate the two overarching themes that shed light on knowledge dynamics in student project teams: the student's individual learning aspirations (1) and the salience of distinctive (functional) roles and knowledge resources amongst the team members (2). To illustrate the lived working practice in student teams and the performed knowledge dynamics/activities with respect to each theme, we present excerpts from our ethnographic study.

4.1. Extension vs. Intensification: Students' Learning Aspirations

The first theme relates to students' individual learning aspirations and expectations for the project. The data from observations and interviews suggest that students' learning aspirations can be positioned on a scale between the acquisition of new knowledge and skills (extension) on the one end and the improvement of existing skills on the other (intensification). In general, however, students performed those tasks that primarily required their existing knowledge and skills as a way to obtain the best possible grades as a team. This objective overruled individual interests to acquire new knowledge and skills, as the following interview quote illustrates²:

I: You have distributed/assigned the work tasks in such a way, that the people do/execute the things they are able to do, did I get that right?

S: Yes. Self-evidently that's not ideal for the learning progress, but for the project's progress you want to make sure to get the best possible grade. We are here to get good marks. Of course we also want to learn, but we seek to utilize the strengths [of everyone] to have a solid result at the end. (Interview S1)

The student's assessment in the quote is in line with data from the observation of project team meetings where the task distribution was discussed with a strong focus on existing expertise and the interpretation of what might be expected by the lecturers to receive the best grade for the output. For some topics such as sustainability or specific project management tasks, the teams could not rely on existing expertise of one of their members and hence the sudden need to extend knowledge arose. Although the students felt that they primarily intensified existing knowledge rather than amplifying it, the evaluation of this circumstance varied substantially.

„I am comfortable with the tasks assigned to me in this project, I'm fully capable to fulfill them as that's what I have done before in other contexts. So principally I am happy with this, but I would have also liked to have a new challenge.“ (Interview S3)

This person clearly expresses the aspiration to expand the knowledge base instead of intensifying existing skills. A fellow student from another project team, however, expressed a different view:

“I'm almost at the end of my studies and I know which topics I want to focus on. Therefore, for me it was a matter of getting better within my focus area and not necessarily to develop expertise for completely new topics.“ (Interview S4)

² The interview quotes have been translated into English by the authors from the original data set.

The students' learning aspirations for the Project Seminar are thus strongly dependent on individual preferences and possibly how advanced they are in their studies. The assignment of tasks in practice is, as illustrated above, mainly influenced by the project teams' objective to obtain the best possible grades and thus based on the question who might be able to complete the task with the best possible result. This practice does not always overlap with the students' individual learning aspirations: Not everyone who wants to learn new skills gets the opportunity, whereas others who might want to intensify their existing skill set may have to expand knowledge in hitherto unknown areas. Knowledge dynamics and the corresponding activities within the project teams are thus taking place in a field of conflict between students' individual learning aspirations and their objective to obtain good marks.

4.2. Negotiating functional Roles within the Team

As one of their first tasks, project teams are required to submit a list with the functional role(s) assigned within the team. The roles (e.g. Project Lead, Construction Lead or Sustainability Expert) are a central didactic element of the PBL approach as they are a way to create a quasi-realistic set-up for students' project work. Usually, the assignment of functional roles is initially understood as a task that has to be completed, rather than an integral part of the project formation process as illustrated by a vignette from a team meeting during the early project phase and an interview quote:

The team's discussion shifts to a new issue: "Ah, and let's distribute those roles prior to the design review. The lecturers seem to be extremely keen on them." The remark immediately triggers a discussion about the plausibility of the roles. The team members are in doubt whether the areas of responsibility for the different roles are clearly demarcated. (field notes team meeting A3)

"The distribution of roles is somewhat artificial and far-fetched. Well, it was required, so we did it. But in fact we are jointly working together on the tasks. So in the end we are effectively all doing the same." (Interview S12)

The interview quote refers to the fluidity of roles amongst team members who are directly involved in the technical construction and development of the prototype: students reported that it frequently happened that when a fellow student was asked for feedback they ended up actively working on the task together instead of just providing feedback to their peers. The students recognized, however, a clear distinction between the roles and tasks associated with project management. Especially the role of Project Lead started to stand out over the course of the semester – not always positively, but in a multi-faceted way that was clearly distinguished from other roles:

"Our team lead is the communication hub to the outside world [i.e. lecturers]" (Interview S22)

"I am not so content with our team lead as I don't have the impression that he has an overview on what's going on in the different work streams and is closely following up on the tasks." (Interview S14)

Although the last quote is critical, it implies an expectation of what kind of activities should be performed by the Project Lead and hence the recognition of the role as a relevant part of the team. In particular, the challenging atmosphere created by the lecturers in the Design Review sessions seemed to foster the crystallisation of the

Project Lead as a distinct role over the course of the semester. Our results thus suggest that, while at the beginning students perceived the distribution of functional roles within their teams as a rather artificial requirement, more clear-cut expectations seemed to emerge over time with respect to roles, which coordinate and communicate tasks within the team and with outsiders.

5 DISCUSSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The students individual learning aspirations vary on a continuum between intensification of existing knowledge and the extension of knowledge to new areas. Our data suggest that these aspirations are not always met in project teams, because students' primary goal is mostly a top grade and this goal might be harder to achieve when learning curves may result in less efficient knowledge activities at least at the outset. On the one hand, these results speak to the value of grades, which apparently functioned as a target unifying the project teams and aligning their everyday working practices. All students strived to achieve the best possible grading for their project deliverables, and this was a common goal they were all working towards. This goal overrode students' individual learning aspirations as tasks were preferably assigned to team members with an existing skillsets.

On the other hand, the results highlight that “knowledge and skills” are primarily categorized by the students as technical or project management skills (such as programming micro-controllers or resource planning). Less quantifiable, meta-level skills and experiences such as teamwork and adaptive communication strategies students did not necessarily perceive as knowledge. This finding relates to a wider discussion on the re-adjustment in engineering curricula to more explicitly target the acquisition of soft skills [17]. Further research to understand students' perception and differentiation of these skills could feed into the successful design of communication and training formats to foster the wider acceptance of soft skills as relevant for professional excellence in engineering practice.

At the beginning of the semester, students furthermore tended to perceive role assignments as an artificial structure imposed by the instructors, which was incongruent with their lived working practice and the way how tasks and deliverables were completed. Yet, over time the emergence of subgroups focusing either on project coordination or product development fostered the perception of distinctive team roles. The relatively large team-size (9-10 members) might have had an impact on the results as the ability of the teams to set up an efficient organisation was decisive. For future research, a comparison with smaller teams would be necessary, yet the ability to manage work within large teams is also a challenge the aspiring engineers would have to overcome in the industry.

The results yield three practical implications for an improved design of PBL courses: (1) In order to support the individual skill development of the students a balanced distribution of experience and skills across the project teams is necessary to shorten the group finding process and more clearly allocate roles and responsibilities within the teams. This could be achieved by lecturers assigning the students to a team based on

each student's expectations, goals, experience and skills as stated prior to the beginning of the course. (2) Reducing the number of management-oriented students while increasing the number of development-oriented students may not only mirror more closely the situation in the industry but also simplify the role identification process as there are now clearer responsibilities within the teams due to an increase of development-related tasks and the decrease of management tasks. (3) Providing a more precise fit of individual work packages and tasks to the functional roles within the team could help to overcome the spontaneous shifts of responsibilities and lead to a more continuous role structure within the teams. To account for a fully virtual teaching situation, the work instructions should be provided in written form and also with documentation templates corresponding to the tasks given (e.g. for the documentation of decisionmaking and development processes). With these changes the student teams should not only be able to install functional roles and assign tasks to individual members more directly but also to stay on track with project management while allowing for and encouraging creativity within those margins.

6 CONCLUSION

This paper illustrates the lived working practice of engineering student teams and the knowledge dynamics emerging in PBL courses. The results revealed opportunities to improve both the setting of the PBL course as well as the evaluation method: Firstly, the formation of the project teams and the functional roles within them would benefit from a centralized assignment of project roles by the lecturers to reduce role-finding conflicts, a more balanced team structure and to incorporate students' individual learning aspirations. Secondly, in-situ ethnographic observation and interviews have proven to be a suitable method for research on students' activities in PBL-courses, as the different observation and interview phases allowed for insights into the lived working practice of student teams.

The study therefore contributes to existing scholarship by providing a student-centred perspective on PBL courses and the knowledge dynamics at play in the project teams. It furthermore highlights the potential for further observation-based research into the role of hard vs. soft skills and the related learning expectations of engineering students to help adjust future teaching curricula to include a balanced combination of both hard *and* soft skills. How to best assess and judge the likelihood that digital engineering task requirements are met by engineers with varying capabilities for managing knowledge dynamics remains, however, an open methodological question, which invites further research in this field.

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